

**THE ROLE OF ANALYTICAL ACTIVITY IN THE PEDAGOGICAL
PROCESS DIRECTED TO THE FORMATION OF CREATIVE
THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENTS**

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ANNOTATION. This article discusses the role of reflection in the formation of creative thinking skills in students, its pedagogical importance, the nature of didactic situations related to the development of reflection, the components and stages of the pedagogical process aimed at this goal, the methods of activity of students, and the work done by teachers. The relationship between creative skills and analytical activity is described. This article can be used by professors, general secondary education teachers, students, researchers, and textbook authors.

Key words: creative thinking, reflection, didactic processes, didactic situations, creative activity, methods of activity, dialogue, cognitive technologies, creative cooperation, teacher, student, imitation games, social experience.

Reflexive processes that encourage students to think creatively have their own specific forms. In the researches of the well-known specialist N.Yu.Postaluk, it was shown that it is a factor that ensures that students have the ability to think creatively, to justify their point of view, to seek explanations, to pose problems, to find answers to them, to be able to adequately assess their own capabilities, and to be able to engage in debates.

Reflection is the initial expression of creative thinking in the student, which is directly related to psychological processes. Analytical activity of the person was

recognized as an object of research in medicine and psychology for the first time. Today, in pedagogy, the analytical activity of the individual is being studied from different angles. With the help of reflexive skills, the student can independently study objects, analyze cause and effect, connections between them, identify objects of research, strive to show his creative potential based on valuable directions, express his views based on creative thinking, self-evaluate, correct and to have the opportunity to work on himself, to show his creative abilities in various forms, to carry out independent research for the purpose of self-development, to determine his own social experience, to evaluate its importance. Analytical activity, that is, reflection, is the main process that encourages a person to think creatively, and is the basis for the formation of creative motives. For example, students perform analytical activities when they read various works of art, get acquainted with examples of fine art, observe the environment, communicate with adults and peers, and strive for creative thinking. Such skills are formed in students during the educational process and create a sufficient basis for their creative thinking. Accordingly, analytical activity is a component of the creative thinking process. Analytical activity is recognized and evaluated by many experts as an integral part of creative activity. It is possible to develop creativity in students by forming analytical activities. Analytical perspective in students ensures that their feelings and experiences are the basis for creative thinking. As a result of such creativity, students' creative thinking becomes a continuous process. In these situations, the teacher should create didactic situations aimed at supporting the analytical activity of the students, supporting the point of view, and ensuring that it turns into a creative thinking process. As a result, students will be able to think creatively after passing the stages of studying, collecting and evaluating scientific information. By involving them in creative activities, the teacher creates a pedagogical opportunity for them to show their existing talents and interests. For students, the level of significance of the studied information increases and becomes a source of creative thinking.

Students' personal experiences can also serve as a source of creative thinking. Because social experience is the basis of students' development and embodies their feelings and experiences. In this process, students demonstrate the knowledge and information they have learned through their practical and creative activities. In this process, students use convenient ways to express creative activity, express their inner experiences, levels of creativity, search for news, and realize their creative potential. At the same time, they evaluate the results of their creative activities, identify gaps and fill them with new methods of action.

As a result of activating students' creative thinking skills, favorable conditions are created for encouraging them to read and learn, mobilizing them to create their own creations, and using methods of intellectual and creative activity. They consist of:

- orientation of the educational process to the formation of students' creative thinking skills;
- regular organization of dialogue situations between the teacher and the student and between the student and the student during the educational process
- expansion of opportunities for students to work in cooperation during the educational process;
- modeling and organization of situations encouraging students to think creatively using various didactic tools;
- creation of a favorable environment for students to independently manage their activities and develop themselves as a result of the development of creative thinking skills.

As a result of such an approach, creativity, regular expansion of one's knowledge, independent learning and development motives arise in students.

Pedagogical processes aimed at forming students' creative thinking skills focus on the following:

- science teachers with high professional skills can clearly imagine the level of creativity formation of educational materials within the scope of the educational subject, systematically apply pedagogical measures and didactic tools aimed at regularly activating the creative skills of students, as a result of such an approach, the ability of students to cognitively accept educational materials develops;

- a special cooperative relationship is created between students with creative thinking skills and science teachers;

- selection, systematization and presentation of didactic tools that serve to develop students' creative thinking skills require special pedagogical and methodical skills from teachers.

The cooperative activity of the teacher and students aimed at the goal of creative development is of special pedagogical importance. The teacher should cooperate with the students to develop their creative thinking skills. It is important to be able to enrich the social experience of learners with the help of didactic tools. As students systematically engage in collaborative relationships with teachers, they are able to enrich their social experiences. This, in turn, serves the formation of creative thinking skills in them.

Development of creative thinking skills in students is one of the leading issues in the theory of developmental education. In this process, the teacher models and organizes pedagogical situations aimed at developing creative thinking skills in students. In such situations, students' creative thinking skills develop systematically and acquire a more practical character. Including:

- incorporation of knowledge and methods of activity encouraging them to think creatively in the content of the educational material presented to the students;

- widespread use of methods of presenting educational materials that affect the emotional sphere of students;

- such as the promotion of subject-subject relations to a new, cooperative stage during the educational process.

It is important that the pedagogical process that encourages students to think creatively includes:

1. Acquisition of cognitive character of the knowledge presented to students; it should be emphasized that situations that develop the student's personality are created by providing educational materials that encourage them to think creatively.
2. Organization of dialogue situations among students in order to determine the level of creative thinking of students; which creates a basis for organizing pedagogical processes aimed at expanding students' creative thinking capabilities. In this process, students compare their ideas with those of their classmates and identify aspects that make them creative.
3. As a result of organizing imitation games among students, they develop creative activity methods such as designing situations, comparing and evaluating events, expressing their views on various events. It is known that simulation games help to develop students' creativity, because they perform analytical activities, express their views, and acquire creative initiative skills.

The model of developmental education allows to systematically organize the activities of students in the process of creative development. For this, teachers will have the opportunity to update students' activities, to look at it as a creative process.

It is to ensure consistency between the presented knowledge and their personal experiences in the formation of students' creative skills. Relying on their personal experiences is of particular importance in the systematic formation of students' creative thinking skills. Students develop creative thinking skills as a result of the development of mental processes. In particular, educational materials that contain knowledge and concepts related to a specific educational subject are a basis for the formation of creative thinking and social experience of students. Such experiences are enriched by students' creative thinking. With the help of social and personal

experiences formed in students as a result of creative thinking, their creative activity methods are expanded. This, in turn, is the basis for raising the creativity of students to a new level. As a result of such activity, the personal experiences of students require making various changes to the projects and models created by them. That's why the formation of an analytical point of view in students takes place in the process of developmental education.

In the process of creative activity, students' personal thoughts and creative qualities develop.

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